

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Annotation: In this article English for preschool children Modern methods of teaching the language are shown the world language is becoming English, so it is taught in school it is necessary to start from age, the article provides information about this.

Key words: foreign language, words, phonetics, Schechter's method, game, methodology, cartoons, riddles.

Аннотация: В этой статье английский язык для детей дошкольного возраста. Показаны современные методы обучения языку. мировой язык становится английским, поэтому его учат в школе начинать необходимо с возраста, информация об этом представлена в статье.

Ключевые слова: иностранный язык, слова, фонетика, метод Шехтера, игра, методика, мультфильмы, загадки.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga ingliz tilini o'rgatishning zamonaviy usullari ko'rsatib o'tilgan bo'lib, hozirgi dunyo tili ingliz tili bo'lib bormoqda, shu bois uni maktabgacha yoshidan boshlash kerak maqola shu haqida ma'lumot beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tili, so'zlar, fonetika, Shexter usuli, O'yin, metodika, multfilmlar, topishmoqlar.

Modern education in the era of flourishing development of the 21st century the place of education and upbringing is extremely important. Current The youth of today is the main foundation in the development of society serves as A well-rounded, well-rounded person formation is the main goal of education and upbringing. Such a person teaching a foreign language to children of preschool age makes a unique contribution. Learning a foreign language is a personal matter for the child development, i.e. multilingual and multicultural in the modern world introduce him to the world of a new language to adapt to the situation creates favorable conditions for foreign language not only schools and in universities, but also many additional

preschool education has become a mandatory component of education in institutions. Demand for a foreign language in society, on the one hand, and also parents language is not only a factor in educating a modern person. If Many years ago, knowledge of the language was required only for jobs in certain fields if so, it was necessary to master at least one of them. Until recently The teaching method was aimed at children of school age, now parents are trying to start learning a foreign language as early as possible. The basics of teaching preschool children a foreign language goals:

- children's basic communication skills in a foreign language formation;
- achieving one's goals, thinking in the context of life communication and the ability to use a foreign language to express feelings;
- create a positive attitude to further study of foreign languages;
- other to arouse interest in the life and culture of countries.

Foreign language to master the psychology of preschool children taking into account we can say that the phonetics of their speech and especially sensitive to intonation, so the education is elementary the main task of the stage is to form correct pronunciation in children with the help of various exercises and special didactic exercises can be achieved, phonetic hearing, as well as speech breathing games in the room are the main tool for development. There is another reason why an early age is preferable for language learning. Teaching children is more than school children and adults age-appropriate based on completely different methodological approaches creativity requires training. Preschool age, English In teaching, children gradually learn the basics of communicative competence develop, this is at the initial stage of learning English includes the following aspects:

- phonetically correct ability to repeat English words teacher, mother tongue or behind the speaker, that is, auditory attention, phonetic hearing and formation of correct pronunciation step by step;
- English word assimilation, integration and activation of wealth;
- known acquisition of a number of simple grammatical structures, coherent statement make up The methodology is to conduct direct educational activities age and individual structure of children's language skills construction and their development taking into account the characteristics should be directed. Communication in a foreign language motivation and should be directed. A child has a positive psychological attitude towards a foreign language it is necessary to create an attitude and create such a positive motivation method is to play. Play is both a form of organization and children are known the method of conducting lessons that accumulate in the amount of English vocabulary, learn lots of poems, songs, rhymes

and more. Playing in the teaching of a foreign language is not against the educational activity, but with it organically related. The method of the game is an imaginary situation Create and accept a certain role by the child or teacher based on doing. Lessons in English are intuitive for children through games practical actions is done by executing through . English in preschool education "Shechter" method of learning a language is a classic "from theory to practice". based not on the model, but on the opposite, more natural system of perception. In this it is very convenient for us to teach children our mother tongue. How are young children? do not know how to speak sentences and speech needed by educators Learn the rules of construction of parts through didactic games teaches the language in modern ways. This technique of the English language is three consists of two stages: the first contains words and phrases, the second and use of grammatical and syntactic structures in the third stage effectiveness from the point of view of educational psychologists enf is one of the successful ones. Children from the beginning of this method to develop a certain style of working in English with, introduction of words that correspond to the most common situations of communication need Such words (greeting, goodbye, short exercises, English use of politeness formulas accepted in the language) allows children to establish a foreign language connection, to English makes the transition easier, let the children know that the lesson has started, now the lesson indicates the passage of a certain stage. The method is successful the most important condition for children's speech-thinking activity is to activate and involve them in foreign language communication. Before school a peculiarity of teaching English to children of age the fact is that he does not just sit at the table and flip through books and notebooks. The process should not be boring, and children should strive for knowledge themselves need Children think clearly, take everything literally they do, they speak. Educational forms are as lexical as possible not to master units, but to cultivate interest in the subject, develop the child's communication skills and express their thoughts should be able to do. Singing children's English alphabet demonstrate that their learning is more effective than mere memorization possible

- games related to mental and physical activities; cartoons;

Although children do not understand the cartoons during language learning, the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters seeks to understand. This is interesting for children and for language learning efficient way.

- role playing (role play) the teacher gives some information, for example, an animal or role playing while learning the names of birds or children should perform.

For example: a student's dog .Another student shows the cat's meowing knowing which animal these sounds belong to, its English it is necessary to say the name.

- subject environment; The teacher creates that environment depending on the topic children learn the language well. For example: traveling, birthday, in the kitchen, etc.]

- through gestures, facial expressions; The teacher said something to the child when speaking or giving a command, for example, come here open the book, stand up, look at the board blackboard) to the child if he uses gestures in such sentences will be clear.

- puzzles; Children's interest in finding answers to riddles strong Therefore, the teacher gives the riddle in English or Uzbek asking the children to say the answer in English must Then children learn words quickly. Let's talk about it In the case of "Fruits", we first learn the names of different fruits we use sounds, children pay close attention to it, and immediately say the names of the fruits: apple, pear, quince... they start.

In conclusion modern language teaching is more cultural new knowledge aimed at forming a person delivery to children through systematic innovative methods is appropriate. A foreign language for preschool children age-appropriate creative and didactic games and open in teaching modern methods of their personal development with training form on the basis of In education, every activity is new successful from information technology and computer devices the use of visual materials is useful for children application of products and strengthening of results.

References:

1. David A. J, Eggen, P. Kauczak. Teaching methods. Promotion of students' learning [M] 2002.
2. Jalolov J.J. Foreign language teaching methodology.-T.: Teacher, 2016.
3. Khaydarova Z.S., teacher of the Department of General Education, Tashkent City Legal Technical University, article "Modern methods of teaching English" 2021. December.
4. Yoldosheva D.A. Innovative methods of teaching English to young children. 2022.